

Response Letter to Reviewers

Dear Don't Look Up team,

We thank your reviews¹ for our first version of the protocol² *'Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref'*. We appreciate the time and effort you put in writing you feedback that has allowed us to improve our workflow both in respect to FAIR principles, in substance and in clarity; the new version can be found [here](#). Since our research is still in progress, we foresee that another revision of the protocol will be needed, and some of the observations will also help us in that context.

Here is a list of your observations that we addressed:

“In order to insert the research in an academic context, it would be relevant to present what is the state of research in this field and how the findings on this question will benefit to the community. I would advise the authors to insert some literature on the subject as references, and some links to the organizations mentioned (DOAJ, Crossref...) to allow the reader to find more information on the subjects if needed.[...]” (Dami, 2022)

“The only suggestion I would make is to better specify the context and motivations of the research. Furthermore, I would add some references to some external resources, in order to give the reader the possibility to consult directly the pages mentioned within the section.” (Bertozzi, 2022)

We partially agree with this statement; we improved the description by adding more context and links to our protocol, but we believe that this is not the place to provide a thorough literature review and state of the art of the research, as that will be included in the article that will be our research output.

“On another note, the PLOS ONE guidelines suggest to include the word “Protocol” in the title of the manuscript.” (Dami, 2022)

“The only two observations to be made are in the numbering of the tasks and the clarification of the variables taken into account.

The first problem can be found in point 2: the text is comparable in importance to the texts of the following sub-points. So I recommend respecting the priority marked by the numbering. The text, in fact, should be a summary of its subsequent sub-tasks” (Bertozzi, 2022)

Thanks for these observations; we changed the title and the sections accordingly, prioritising the comprehension of the sections.

“[...]there is a minor difference between what has been announced in the abstract and what is actually carried out in the protocol. Indeed, the abstract states that the analysis will be carried out by querying the DOAJ API, while the first step of the protocol mentions the public data dump of the journals. [...] after step 3, there is no indication on where the information about the agency responsible for the DOIs will be stored: will it be added to one of the preexisting two datasets or will it be stored in

¹ Constance Dami. (2022). Review of: "Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/MOBTWR and Alessandro Bertozzi. (2022). Review of: "Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/V2LBTO.

² Davide Brembilla, Chiara Catizone, Giulia Venditti . Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref. [protocols.io/https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxyqzx7yww8j/v1](https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxyqzx7yww8j/v1)

a new one? Such a precision was present in the previous steps and should be added here to ensure that someone replicating the experiment would obtain the same datasets in the same formats as the authors at each step. [...] Links to the mentioned tools are provided, except in the case of step 3 which could be transformed in a link.” (Dami, 2022)

“The other problem concerns points 1 and 2. The second point specifies the use of ISSNs to send a request to the API. However, it does not specify that the ISSN is part of the unique identifiers downloaded previously. I recommend adding this specification to make it easier for non-experts to read.” (Bertozzi, 2022)

Thanks for the observations. We have changed the protocol accordingly and as well as the abstract; the difference, as well as the inconsistency in the methodologies were rooted in the fact that we were still familiarising with the tools necessary to obtain the information we needed.

“It would be correct to specify the reasons for certain choices: in point 6 it is specified a formula to calculate the "effect size", but without any reflection on the reasons for this choice” (Bertozzi, 2022)

“I would suggest adding a link to the test analysis mentioned, to make it more explicit to a non-initiated reader.” (Dami, 2022)

We thank you for this observation. In the new version of the protocol, we include the measures we will obtain from the study, while the effect size was dropped as we need time to review whether it will be useful to add.

“At this stage of research there are no outputs, but there is no indication in the protocol on how and where the data found will be published and this information should be added.” (Dami, 2022)

We agree with this crucial observation. We also included a link the new version of our Data Management Plan³, which explains the datasets we are using for our research.

We thank our reviewers again for this opportunity in improving our research output. We look forward to hearing from you in due time regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

La Chouffe Team 09/05/2022

³ Davide Brambilla, Chiara Catizone, & Giulia Venditti. (2022). Revised DMP - La Chouffe (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6491625>

References:

Alessandro Bertozzi. (2022). Review of: "Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/V2LBTO.

Davide Brembilla, Chiara Catizone, Giulia Venditti . Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref. **protocols.io**<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygxz7yww8j/v1>

Davide Brambilla, Chiara Catizone, & Giulia Venditti. (2022). Revised DMP - La Chouffe (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6491625>

Constance Dami. (2022). Review of: "Availability of Open Citations from Open Journals in Crossref v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/MOBTWR